

IMPLICATIONS OF INFLATION ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA (2000-2022)

***¹Amadi, Kevin T. PhD (ECONS), Ph.D (BAM) and ²Ibeaja, Uzoma. F. PhD (ACCTS),
Ph.D (ECONS)**

¹Department. of Economics, Gregory University, Uturu, Abia State, Nigeria

²Department. of Accountancy, Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the implications of inflation on economic growth in Nigeria from 2000 to 2022. Data were tested using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test. And Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL), Diagnostic Tests of Normality, Serial Correlation, and Heteroskedasticity proved validity of the model. The ARDL test established a long run relationship between inflation and economic growth in Nigeria. The result also revealed that inflation had negative relationship with economic growth; employment had positive relationship with economic growth, while Gross Fixed Capital Formation had negative relationship with economic growth. The explanatory variables INF, EMP, and GFCF showed a significant joint effect and accounted for 99.45% of the total variation in economic growth. The concluded that there is a long run relationship between inflation and economic growth in Nigeria, and recommended that the Central Bank of Nigeria should step up efforts to reduce money supply and/or good interest rate management. The Nigerian government should implement policies that will boost employment level in the country to assist in controlling inflation.

KEYNOTES: *Implication, Inflation, Economic Growth*

INTRODUCTION

The need to understand the dynamics of inflation is central to the success of monetary and even fiscal policy to ensure the achievement of price stability. Understanding inflation dynamics, may help to ascertaining its determinants an effective way of predicting its future path. For most advanced countries, the maintenance of price stability continues to be the overriding objective of monetary policy. The emphasis given to price stability in the conduct of monetary policy is with a view to promoting sustainable growth and development as well as strengthening the purchasing power of the domestic currency. They employ monetary policy frameworks/instruments considered best suited for achieving this mandate (Amadi, 2023).

The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) employs the monetary targeting framework in its monetary policy. This is based on the assumption of a stable and predictable relationship between the money supply and inflation. Consequently, the achievement of this objective is important given the numerous adverse effects of price instability on other macroeconomic prices such as the exchange rate, interest rate, the wage rate and macroeconomic performance, (Nwaru, 2022).

Currently, high inflation is one of the main negative features of the Nigerian economy. Several attempts have been made by different relevant authorities in Nigeria at arresting this economic menace, these

efforts have not achieved much. However, for monetary or fiscal policy to achieve the stipulated objective of price stability there would be crucial, (Doguwa, 2013).

Generally, high inflation imposes welfare costs on a nation, hinders efficient allocation of resources by affecting the role of changes in the relative price level discourages investments and savings in an economy as it creates unpredictable future prices. The situation also affects financial development because it makes financial intermediation more costly, and the poor are mostly affected because they rescind in holding financial assets that provide a hedge against high inflation and decrease a country international competitiveness by making exports more expensive. It also has a negative effect on payments balance, and business and households perform poorly during periods of high inflation (Frimpong & Oteng-Abayie, 2010).

Inflation in an economy can be measured using consumer price index approach and the wholesale or producer price index approach. The period changes in the wholesale or producer price index are used as direct measures of inflation, though not the best measure of inflation in Nigeria because of her peculiar economic situation which has defiled most macroeconomic policies in the world today. The consumer price index (CPI) approach, the other hand, is the least efficient of the approaches used in measuring inflation rates in Nigeria, yet it is the most used measure of inflation, as it is easily and currently available on monthly, quarterly and annual basis (CBN, 2022).

In Nigeria, high inflation has undesirable consequences on economic parameters. Just as Ofor, Amadi and Ibeaja (2022), high rate of inflation in the economy would reduce demand for bank's financial assets and hence impair the process of financial intermediation in the banking sector as deposits would move from the banking system into real estate and inventory speculations, among others.

The Nigerian economy has remained largely underdeveloped, despite the increases in growth rate. The challenges of high inflationary pressure, unemployment, high exchange rate, debt overhang, adverse balance of payments and high interest rates, thus causing economic recession and depression. This has been described as exclusive growth, which is worrisome, disturbing and calls for concern as it contradicts macroeconomic policies such as the Philips curve.

Noticeably, one would agree with us that the Nigerian economic situation, having defiled the workable macroeconomic policies in other nations of the world, thus, needs an indebted study to determine the implications of inflation on the Nigeria's economic growth.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to establish the implications of inflation on the economic growth in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- a) Determine the effects of inflation on the Nigeria's economic growth.
- b) Examine the effects of employment on the Nigeria's economic growth.
- c) Establish the effects of gross fixed capital formation on the Nigeria's economic growth.

Research Hypotheses

H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between inflation and economic growth in Nigeria.

H_{02} : There is no significant relationship between employment level and economic growth in Nigeria.

H_{03} : There is no significant relationship exists between gross fixed capital formation and economic growth in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework

The Inflation

Tugba, Dayioglu, Yilmaz & Aydin (2020), an economic situation in which the increase in money supply is growing "faster" than the new production of goods and services in the same economy. In addition, most economists usually try to distinguish inflation from an economic phenomenon of a one-time increase in prices or price increases in a narrow group of economic goods or services.

According to DinhD (2020), inflation is a general and persistent increase in the prices of goods and services in an economy. The inflation rate is measured as the percentage change in the price index (consumer price index, wholesale price index, price index).

Nzotta (2021), opined that the consumer price index (CPI), for instance, measures the price of a representative basket of goods and services purchased by the average consumer and is calculated on a periodic survey of consumer prices. Owing to the different basket weights, changes in the price of some goods and services have varying degree impact on measured inflation.

Another measure of inflation or price movements is GDP Deflator. This is available on an annual basis. However, it is rarely used as an indicator of inflation. The CPI represents the cost of living and is, therefore, more appropriate for measuring people's welfare. Furthermore, because CPI is available more frequently, it is useful for monetary policy purposes.

According to Mukhtar and Muhammad (2017), most researchers, policymakers and economists agree that zero inflation is not healthy for an economy and should be discouraged. This is because deflation has serious effects on country's economic growth and development. Thus, moderate inflation enhances nation's domestic economic growth and development. Where as high inflation is detrimental to domestic economic growth and development. In view of the above, policymakers and monetary authorities are advised to work toward achieving a low rate of inflation in an economy, that would help maximize the overall economic well-being of citizens in their countries.

In Nigeria, high inflation is one of the major challenges facing the nation's economy. The government inability to provide a lasting solution to this problem indicates the inevitability of inflation in the economy; hence, it shows that the government lacks the power to eliminate the persistent rising prices of goods and services in the economy (Taiwo, 2011).

Trend between inflation and economic growth in Nigeria

The facts and figures obtained from the IMF World Economic Outlook Report (2011) revealed that the Nigeria's GDP tends to be low when inflation rates are high, apart from a few years of the 1980's. For example, the 1998 GDP growth rate was relatively high in the middle of inflationary levels at the time. This could be a positive effect of increased domestic productivities, which was the major thrust of SAP in the sense that domestic output increased.

The trend of inflation between 2001 and 2010 in Nigeria at the average level is in the double-digit rate, but the GDP growth seems unimpressive, which could be attributed to petroleum export proceeds. The inflation rate was 18.87 in 2001, 12.88 in 2002, 14.03 in 2003, 15.00 in 2004, 17.86 in 2005, 8.23 in 2006, 5.39 in 2007, 11.58 in 2008, 12.54 in 2009 and 13.74 in 2010 by 2021, and it was 16.95 and 18.85 in 2022 with the corresponding real GDP growth rates within these years as 26658.62, 30745.19, 33004.80, 36057.74, 38378.80, 40703.68, 43385.88, 46320.01, 50042.36, 54612.26, 72393.67, 72176.49 respectively.

Despite the relatively good annual GDP growth rate, the poverty level and unemployment continue to grow. The level of investment does not match with the growth level because the inflation constitutes risk. It therefore the inflation level in Nigeria is disincentive investment and is not likely to translate to sustainable development eventually.

Theoretical Review

The Monetary Theory of Inflation

Monetarism refers to the followers of Milton Friedman (1867-1960) who hold that only money matters and that monetary instruments are more potent instruments of price and economic stabilization than fiscal policy. This school is known as the modern quantity theory of money which holds that inflation is always and everywhere a monetary phenomenon, which comes from rapid expansion in the quantity of money than the expansion in the quantity of output. That is, if the money supply rises faster than the expansion in the quantity of output of national income than inflation will occur. According to Totonchi (2011), monetarists employed the familiar identity of the exchange equation of Fisher, i.e the Quantity theory of Money (Fisher version).

$$MV=PT$$

Where: M= money supply; V= velocity of circulation; P=price level; T=transactions.

T is believed to measure output and as such is often substituted for Y (national income). The above equation must hold ($MV=PY$), that is, the rate of expenditure must equal the value of output. However, they argued that it is unwarranted increases in the money supply that manifest in inflation.

Keynesian Inflation Theory

John Maynard Keynes (1883-1946) and his followers believed that increase in aggregate demand is the source of demand-pull inflation. Demand pull inflation is where the total demand for goods and services is in excess of the aggregate supply and provisions of goods and services in the economy. The aggregate demand in this sense comprises of consumption, investment and government expenditure.

According to Totonchi (2011), a policy that causes the decrease in each component of total demand is effective in reduction of pressure on demand and invariably inflation. This basically involves reduction in government expenditures, increase in tax as well as controlling the volume of money.

In Nigeria, where the economy can hardly produce output to meet up with economy's demand which is highly foreign goods dependent, which may be faced with more inflationary pressures due to excess demand. When taxes are increased as the producers may get involved more in rent seeking economic activities rather getting involved in the real sectors of the economy which can tackle the problem of low productivity and unemployment, inflation results.

Empirical Review

Onwubuariri, Oladeji and Bank-Ola, (2021), examined the nexus between inflation rate and economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1979-2019 by using Johansen-Juselius co-integration technique, ordinary least squares (OLS) approach, Granger causality technique. The empirical results indicated that inflation rate has negative relationship with real gross domestic product, while exchange rates and interest rates have positive and insignificant relationship with inflation rate in the economy. The results of the Granger causality revealed that causality does not run between inflation rate and real gross domestic product in the economy. However, unidirectional causality runs from exchange rate to real gross domestic product.

Nzotta (2021), investigated the impact of unemployment and inflation economic growth in Nigeria from 1986 to 2010 by employing Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) approach, Johansen co-integration test and Granger causality test. The results of the stationarity test showed that all the variables were stationary at first difference. The results of the Johansen co-integration test indicated long run relationship among economic growth, unemployment and inflation. The results of the Granger causality showed that unemployment and inflation granger cause RGDP in the economy.

Aminu, Manuand and Salihu (2013), studied the impact of inflation on GDP in the economy of Pakistan from 1972 to 2010, using ordinary least square (OLS) technique. The variables used in the investigation include gross domestic product (GDP) growth rate used as dependent variable; whereas consumer price index (CPI) proxied for inflation, trade openness (OPNS) and investment growth rate (INVG) were used as the independent variables. The results showed that inflation has negative and significant impact on the growth of Pakistani economy.

Ezeanyejí and Ugochukwu (2015), investigated the effect of inflation on economic growth in Nigeria from 1991 to 2013 using Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method of simple regression model. The variables used in the investigation include gross domestic product (GDP) as the dependent variable, whereas inflation rate (INF) is the independent variable. The results showed that inflation has negative impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

Aminu and Manu (2014), investigated the nature of the relationship between inflation and economic growth in Nigeria using annual time series data from 1980 to 2013. The variables used for the study are Gross Domestic Product (GDP) as a dependent variable, while the independent variables are: Inflation rate, Exchange Rate (EXCHR), input of labor and Capital. The study used the Ordinary Least Square to capture the impact of the dependent variable on the independent variables. The result showed that inflation has positive impact on economic growth in Nigeria. In a similar study, Idris and Suleiman (2019), investigated the influence of inflation on economic growth of Nigeria from 1980 to 2017. The study employed Vector Error Correction mechanism on variables selected, which are gross domestic product, inflation rate, interest rate, and exchange rate in the country. Findings reveal long run relationship among the variables and that inflation rate and interest rate affect the economic growth of Nigeria significantly and negatively in the long run.

Inim, Samuel and Prince (2020), examined aside money supply, other determinants of inflation in Nigeria using the Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method on quarterly data from 1999-

2018. Their findings showed that poor infrastructural development, exchange rate, political instability, corruption, and double taxation significantly stimulate inflation. The results showed a causal relationship between these other determining factors and inflation. The ARDL result showed a significant long-short run relationship.

Adaramola and Dada (2020), examined the influence of inflation on Nigeria's economic growth prospects. The study findings indicated that inflation and real exchange rate significantly negatively impact economic growth, while the interest rate and money supply indicate a positive and significant impact on economic growth. The causality result also shows the unidirectional relationships between interest rate, exchange rate, government consumption expenditures and gross domestic product, while inflation and the degree of openness showed no causal relationship with gross domestic product.

Idris and Bakar (2017), explored Nigeria's inflationary trend to determine its impact on economic growth. The study employed a descriptive method and further used charts to show the inflationary trend and GDP growth to better understand how Nigeria's inflation rates affect the desired economic growth level. The study concluded that Nigeria's current inflationary trend negatively affects sustainable growth and development, meaning that one of the requirements for reaching the desired growth level in Nigeria is to control the excessive increase in the inflation rate.

DinhD (2020), investigated the relationship between inflation and economic growth for Brazil for the period between 1980 and 1995 with the result establishing a negative relationship in the short run but that inflation does not affect economic growth in the long run. These could be a situation where the scope of production can change to absorb the lag of excess demand.

METHODOLOGY

Model Specification

The model of this study is functionally expressed as:

$$RGDP=f(NF,EMP,,GFCF)1$$

The econometric model of equation 1 is presented as:

$$RGDP = a_0 + a_1NF_t + a_2EMP_t + a_3GFCF_t + \mu_t2$$

Where:

RGDP=Real Gross Domestic Product

NF=Inflation

EMP=Employment

GFCF=Gross Fixed Capital Formation

$a_0 = Intercept$

$a_1 - a_3 = are$ coefficients of the estimated parameters

$\mu_t = Error$ term

A Priori expectation: $a_1 < 0$; $a_2, a_3 > 0$

Method of Data Analysis

ARDL Bounds Tests for Cointegration

The ARDL of the model is specified as;

$$RGDP = a_0 + RGDP_{t1} + a_1NF_t + a_1NF_{t-1} + a_2EMP_t + a_2EMP_{t1} + a_3GFCF_t + a_3GFCF_{t-1} + e_t$$

e_t Descriptive Statistics Results

Subject	LOGRGDP	INF	LOGGFCF	EMP
Mean	11	12.62652	9.115972	58.98
Median	10.95973	12.54	9.125116	60.23
Maximum	11.18987	18.87	9.345383	60.41
Minimum	10.13339	5.39	8.833527	55.27
Std.Dev.	0.346123	3.807985	0.143238	1.630937
Skewness	-0.677919	-0.048576	-0.449444	-0.857115
Kurtosis	2.121981	2.159071	2.221012	2.524884
Jarque-Bera	2.500496	0.686742	1.355872	3.032475
Probability	0.286434	0.709375	0.507664	0.219536
Sum	249.2694	290.41	209.6674	1356.54
SumSq.Dev.	2.635629	319.0165	0.451374	58.519

Source: Output of E-view 10

Unit Root Test

Unit Root Result

ENTRIES	ADF statistic at stationary point	5% sig. Level	Levels P-value	1 st Difference P=value	Order of integration
LOGRGDP	-5.422718	-3.004861	0.0002	0.2620	1(0)
INF	-4.420054	-3.029970	0.0647	0.0029	1(1)
LOGGFCF	-10.05613	-3.020686	0.5838	0.0000	1(1)

EMP	-2.866550	-1.958088	0.2547	0.0064	1(1)
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Source: Output of E-views 10.

Lag Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-	NA	0.016876	7.269374	7.467746	7.316105
	75.96312					
1	4.409058	124.2115*	5.01e-05*	1.417358*	2.409215*	1.651010*

Source: E-views 10 Output.

Autoregressive Distributive Lag Analysis (ARDL) Test.

ARDL Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
LOGRGDP(-1)	0.931109	0.029239	31.84511	0.0000
INF	-0.003177	0.001484	-2.141019	0.0471
LOGGFCF	-0.044926	0.061199	-0.734095	0.4729
EMP	0.000916	0.004327	0.211753	0.8348
C	1.189928	0.538421	2.210031	0.0411
R-squared	0.995545	Mean dependent var		10.86982
Adjusted R-squared	0.994496	S.D.dependent var		0.317496
S.E. of regression	0.023554	Akaike info criterion		-4.462347
Sum squared resid	0.009431	Schwarz criterion		-4.214382
Log likelihood	54.08581	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-4.403934
F-statistic	949.6805	Durbin-Watson stat		2.138946
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Output of E-views 10.

ARDL Long Run Form and Bounds Test and Error Correction Model

Bounds F-statistic 25.48840	Lower Bound	2.79
	Upper Bound	3.67
ECM	Coefficient -0.068891	Probability 0.0000

Source: Researcher's Extract from E-view 10

Test of Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between inflation and economic growth in Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between employment and economic growth in Nigeria.

Ho₃: Significant relationship does not exist between gross fixed capital formation and economic growth in Nigeria.

Discussion of the findings

The t-statistic value of inflation as -2.141019 and the probability value as 0.0471 showed that there is significant relationship between inflation and economic growth in Nigeria.

The t-statistic value of employment as 0.211753 and the probability value as 0.8348 proved that there is no significant relationship between employment and economic growth in Nigeria.

The t-statistic value of Gross fixed capital formation as -0.734095 and the probability value is 0.4729 showed that significant relationship does not exist between Gross Fixed Capital Formation and economic growth in Nigeria.

Conclusion

The model of the study revealed that changes in inflation strongly explained the changes in economic growth in Nigeria. Therefore, it was concluded that inflation has a significant negative short run, but long run positive effects on economic growth in Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. The central bank of Nigeria should step up efforts to reduce money supply and/or good interest rate management.
2. The Nigerian government at the states and federal levels should proffer policies that will boost employment level in the country to assist control inflationary level.
3. The central bank of Nigeria should place effective surveillance on the deployment of the formed capital to a positive and significant advantage in the general economy.

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